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Ag₃[PMo₁₂O₄₀]: An efficient and green catalyst for the synthesis of highly functionalized pyran-annulated heterocycles via multicomponent reaction

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Abstract

A facile, efficient and eco-friendly catalytic protocol was developed for the synthesis of medicinally important pyran-annulated heterocycles via multicomponent reaction (MCR). Cyclocondensation of differently substituted aromatic aldehydes, malononitrile/ethyl cyanoacetate and various β -dicarbonyl compounds in the presence of Ag₃[PMo₁₂O₄₀] \cdot nH₂O as heterogeneous catalyst, in EtOH–H₂O, afforded diverse pyran-fused chromene analogues. The merits observed for this approach were it being conducted via MCR, using commercially available or easily accessible starting materials in the presence of a green and easily separable heterogeneous and reusable catalyst, and affording high yields of desired products in very short reaction times with high purity in one-pot fashion, thus providing a superior alternative approach for the synthesis of pyran-annulated heterocycles.

Keywords: 2-amino-4H-pyrans, Ag₃[PMo₁₂O₄₀], heterogeneous catalysis, multicomponent reaction, one-pot synthesis, polyoxometalates, Catalysis, Multi-component reactions, Catalysts